

SATRE 2.0

Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments 2.0 Architecture Report

1. Approach

To provide the greatest utility a multi-level architectural approach has been used to create a standard architecture which Trusted Research Environment (TRE) implementers can use. This standardised architecture aims to improve decision-making, enhance agility and flexibility, optimise costs, aid interoperability, improve compliance and improve communication between implementers.

The broader SATRE specification which contains more detail about the requirements for implementing TREs safely can be found at [the specification site](#). The architecture and associated models have been created in collaboration with the wider SATRE team, and through community engagement across the TRE community in the UK.

Version 2 was developed as part of the DARE UK TREvolution programme and has been extended to include federation of TREs to safely bring data together from multiple trusted environments.

In architecture as with statistics “all models are wrong, but some are useful” (George E. P. Box). These models should not be considered authoritative or prescriptive. For the architectural models to provide utility we should understand the outputs in two key dimensions: audience and purpose.

1.1. Dimension 1 – Audience

This document and associated models are intended for use by designers and builders of trusted research environments including research infrastructure developers and enterprise and solution architects.

1.2. Dimension 2 – Purpose

This architecture will serve as a tool to:

- Help implementers design and implement environments within a variety of organisations using a mix of existing and novel technologies.
- Provide insight into the underlying components of a TRE and allow improvement planning and road mapping.
- Provide a common understanding of the component elements of a TRE, what functionality they provide and how they fit together to the TRE user community.
- Facilitate the communication of how one or many TREs function alone or together through federation.

1.3. Architecture Views

Within this document there are multiple views provided including capability map view, capability decompositions and 5 safes process view. More views can be created to highlight or demonstrate elements and relationships.

2. Using the Architecture and Specification

The SATRE architecture, specification and supporting models are open source and available via the links below.

2.1. Download and Extend the ArchiMate Models

The ArchiMate source files for the SATRE architecture are published in the SATRE GitHub organisation. You can clone or download the repository and open the models in the open source tool Archi to view, edit and extend them locally. Collaborative editing and synchronisation across contributors is supported via the coArchi plugin.

SATRE ArchiMate repository: <https://github.com/sa-tre/satre-archimate>

2.2. Explore the Architecture Online

The SATRE 2.0 architecture can be explored interactively through the online architecture explorer. The explorer provides a navigable view of the capability map, capability decompositions and the relationships between components without the need to install a modelling tool.

Architecture explorer: <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/>

2.3. Read the Detailed Specification

The full SATRE specification is published on Read the Docs. It contains the architectural principles, capability definitions, requirement statements and evaluation guidance that accompany the architecture in this document.

SATRE specification (latest): <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/v2.0.0/specification.html>

3. Overview

The SATRE architecture is universally applicable to all TRE implementations and is documented in three parts, principles, capabilities and capability decompositions.

Architecture principles provide fundamental guidelines that inform the design, decision making and implementation for a TRE. These principles provide a framework to ensure that the design of the underlying components of a TRE are aligned to consistent goals, values and best practices. These principles can be found in the [main SATRE specification site](#).

Capabilities are an ability that an organisation needs to deliver a TRE safely. Capabilities are realised through a combination of organisation, people, processes, applications and technology. The capability map in section 4 provides a structure for organising and understanding the capabilities. It helps identify, define, and categorise the key elements needed to create and operate a TRE.

Capability decompositions map out the components that realise a capability. These components will vary depending on the nature of the capability. Business focused capabilities will be primarily realised by business processes, roles and services with more technology focused capabilities realised by applications, interfaces and technology.

There are multiple requirements associated with each capability. These are documented in the specification, linked in this architecture, and provide guidance on how the capability can be delivered safely.

3.1. Metamodel

Below is the metamodel to which the architecture conforms. The decomposition elements of people (actors and roles), processes, data and applications combine to provide an organisation with the ability to fulfil or realise a requirement. Business processes are triggered by events such as changes or requests. Applications serve those business processes reading, writing and modifying data elements.

Figure 1: SATRE metamodel diagram showing components realising a capability related to the specification requirement.

4. Capability Map

The capability map represents all the capabilities an implementing organisation needs to run a TRE safely. In SATRE v2.0 the architecture has been extended to five pillar capabilities, adding a Federation pillar to reflect the growing importance of federated TRE operations.

Figure 2: 5 pillars containing 36 capabilities needed to deliver a safe TRE

Information Governance – What the organisation does to ensure information risk is measured and managed to an acceptable level.

Computing Technology – What the organisation does to manage systems for storing, processing, retrieving, and sending information.

Data Management – What the TRE organisation does to manage data assets and ensure information remains secure.

Federation Extension – What a federation of TREs does to govern, coordinate and operate a multiple TREs that work together to support research across organisations.

Supporting Capabilities – These organisational abilities are likely to be shared across the wider enterprise and unlikely to relate solely to a TRE. For example, procurement is likely to be part of a finance function and while the TRE organisation may stress the need to secure supply chains as part of procurement it is unlikely to need a parallel procurement capability for the TRE.

There will be considerable variation in how supporting capabilities work to within an organisation. Due to these variations the supporting capabilities are not modelled as decompositions in the architecture.

5. Capability Decompositions

1.1 Information Governance

What the organisation does to ensure information risk is measured and managed to an acceptable level.

Figure 3: Information Governance capability decomposition

Information governance requirements are defined by top management within the TRE implementing organisation. These will be drawn from the context of the organisation, the work it performs and the nature of the data it processes. Gathering and monitoring these requirements is a key process for ensuring the TRE aligns with the requirements. This requirements process will trigger the control process which decides actions taken to control risk. Control implementation requires prioritisation and resourcing, resources are allocated through the resource allocation process. The TRE top management must have control of adequate resources to control risk and suitable authority to act. Quality data is a key input to measuring and improving the effectiveness of the TRE in relation to governance, risk and compliance.

1.2. Quality Management

What the organisation does to measure and control quality of processes, documentation and outputs.

Figure 4: Quality Management capability decomposition

Quality management reporting is continual but may be triggered by a scheduled event (such as governance meeting). Internal audits will be triggered according to a policy or an issue or change. Supplier management and monitoring will be continual but may also be triggered by a change or addition of a supplier. The issue process will be triggered by an adverse event, incident or audit outcome. Document and SOP and Asset management are continually running.

Quality management data is crucial to understanding whether the organisation is operating as intended. The quality manager role is responsible for keeping the TRE operating within risk tolerance with an internal auditor assessing the effectiveness of the TRE through the internal audit processes.

Measurement is a key element to quality management all processes across the TRE will generate data, those data must be trusted, retained and be made available to the quality manager and internal auditor during an audit.

Documentation is a key control across the TRE for example, policies, SoPs, work instructions and contracts. Control of these documents is critical to the operation of the TRE and maintaining quality.

Quality management processes and data can be extremely complex and the ability to collate, measure, report and track data across many processes can be daunting. The implementation of an electronic quality management system that tracks all the processes within the capability and draws data from multiple sources for alerting and reporting purposes can reduce the overhead of maintaining the quality management system.

1.3. Risk Management

What the organisation does to ensure information risk is measured and managed to an acceptable level.

Figure 5: Risk Management capability decomposition

Risk within the TRE organisation is ultimately owned by the top management with risk ownership for data assets delegated to information asset owners. Risks related to operations are assessed and treated by operational teams.

Risk ownership involves the understanding of risk appetite within the organisation and agreement to proceed with operations given the current or future risk landscape. The risk assessment process scores risk according to an agreed matrix usually based on likelihood and impact. Once a risk is assessed the risk treatment process is triggered applying both technical, policy and process controls to bring them within accepted tolerances. Where risks fall outside of the automatically accepted tolerances, they will be escalated to risk owners.

1.4. Study Management

What the organisation does to create and maintain research projects and work packages within the TRE.

Figure 6: Study Management capability decomposition

A TRE may have a single study or contain many separate studies. Where there are multiple studies, each study must be separately identified and logically isolated from others.

A study (sometimes called a project or work package) has a lifecycle. Beginning with an initial setup to bring a study onboard. Once within the TRE, compliance with internal and external standards must be checked as the project evolves and regulations and policies change.

The study onboarding process is triggered by the information asset owner. Compliance checks can be triggered by the information asset owner and the onboarding process or through a scheduled event like an audit or change. Study closure is triggered by the information asset owner or a scheduled event such as a contract termination.

Within the data asset and study register critical information related to the study will be maintained. These metadata will include study role information, contracts, data management plans and finance information along with links to quality data related to the study held, for example, user permissions and training records.

In order to allow owners and managers to manage their studies data must be provided to them, Ideally this would be through a portal. The portal can also provide a self-service interface to ensure the study data is correct within the registers.

1.5. Researcher Accreditation

Ability to ensure that people with access to data are identified correctly and they are suitably qualified.

Figure 7: Researcher Accreditation capability decomposition

Information asset owners make access changes to the permissions on assets they own to provide access to researchers and data consumers. These changes trigger the identification process to ensure that the right user is given access to the resource. Once identified the onboarding process accesses the user identity attribute data.

Researcher accreditation identifies TRE users and brings them into the environment. All users within the TRE will pass through the identity verification process, data related to the person will be recorded and then they are issued with an identity, password and other authentication factors. This process will also involve agreements such as fair usage statements, contracts and terms of service etc.

1.6. Training Management and Delivery

Ability to deliver, track and maintain adequate training levels to ensure competence of all people within the TRE organisation.

Figure 8: Training Management and Delivery capability decomposition

Course data is created and maintained by the curriculum creation and management process. Certification is issued as part of the training record following the completion of courses using the learning management system application.

Competency of people within the TRE is a key control for risk across multiple roles and processes. To ensure competency a training curriculum should be developed with training needs aligned to roles within the TRE. This training should be delivered through a learning management system and certification and training record maintained for users within the TRE. Competency may be proven through professional qualifications or external training in which case certifications should be accepted when issued by a trusted third party.

1.7. Public Involvement and Engagement

What the organisation does to involve the public in the governance and operation of the TRE.

Figure 9: Public Involvement and Engagement capability decomposition

Public involvement and engagement (PIE) within a TRE organisation recognises that the public are key stakeholders in research data use, and that their trust must be actively earned and maintained. This encompasses both the involvement of public members in governance and oversight roles, and the broader engagement of the public with information about TRE operations and research outcomes.

Public members may participate directly in TRE governance through advisory panels, lay membership of oversight committees, or structured consultation processes. A Public Engagement Specialist role supports the design and delivery of involvement activities, ensuring these are accessible, meaningful and representative.

Involvement activities should be documented and their influence on TRE decisions recorded to demonstrate accountability.

Broader public engagement is achieved through the proactive publication of information about TRE operations, research outputs and data use decisions. This includes disclosure of information governance incidents where appropriate, ensuring the public can make informed judgements about the trustworthiness of the organisation.

2.0. Computing Technology

What the organisation does to manage systems for storing, processing, retrieving, and sending information.

Figure 10: Computing Technology capability decomposition

Computing technology requirements are defined by top management within the TRE organisation in collaboration with TRE operators and developers and researchers themselves. Requirements are drawn from information governance requirements which primarily specify the controls needed within the technical and computing infrastructure. Researcher personas influence them according to the technical knowledge and experience of researchers along with the work they need to perform within the system, for example, a data scientist will have very different requirements to a clinician. The required compute resources will vary according to the scale of data and computational techniques employed during research.

2.1. End User Computing

The ability of the TRE operator to provide and manage devices, workspaces, interfaces and applications used by researchers to interact with underlying systems and data.

Figure 11: End User Computing capability decomposition

End user computing is realised by interfaces and applications providing researchers and data consumers access to data. Changing researcher requirements trigger the application deployment process to update applications and interfaces. The advanced and cluster computing technology service provides resources for advanced analytics capabilities such as high-performance / high throughput computing and Machine Learning.

The TRE may contain a single or multiple end user computing environments. Multiple computing interfaces provide familiar and flexible ways for users to interact with data. Interfaces may also provide an opportunity to obfuscate data by allowing the submission of code without providing direct access to the data itself. Tools to version control code support reproducible science. Artifact management applications allow users limited access to external repositories outside the environment.

2.2. Infrastructure Management

The ability of the TRE operator to instantiate, deploy, change or remove deployed infrastructure.

Figure 12: Infrastructure Management capability decomposition

Infrastructure developers and TRE operators deploy and manage infrastructure within the TRE. Infrastructure is likely to be in part or fully virtualised allowing the automation of deployment processes.

The change process is triggered by an improvement activity (e.g. risk reduction or user requirement) and ensures infrastructure changes are risk assessed, carefully managed and recorded.

Infrastructure is decommissioned ensuring data and infrastructure services are managed off the platform. Availability management ensures infrastructure maintains uptime with data and systems available as agreed with service users. There will be a set of management applications including, crucially network management ensures the technical environment remains suitably isolated.

2.3. Capacity Management

What the organisation does to ensure the right amount of resources are available at the right time to provide a service.

Figure 13: Capacity Management capability decomposition

Capacity planning looks at patterns of activity, compute and storage requirements in order to determine suitable resources for deployment into the TRE infrastructure. The main control for capacity is finance and billing processes to ensure operational and capital costs can be recovered to ensure the TRE is sustainable and remains available to users. Capacity increases identified in the planning process trigger the billing process and update financial data.

2.4. Configuration Management

What the organisation does to identify, maintain, and verify information on IT assets and configurations in the TRE organisation.

Figure 14: Configuration Management capability decomposition

TRE Builders and Developers create and change the TRE, including the deployment of physical infrastructure, software and code. In order to control risk within the TRE, configuration of hardware, software and code should be carefully designed and planned through the configuration management processes. Changes to any part of the hardware, infrastructure or software triggers updates to infrastructure asset data and configuration data.

2.5. Information Security

What the organisation does to safeguard research to ensure the confidentiality, integrity and availability of research resources and data.

Figure 15: Information Security capability decomposition

Information Security is delivered via the combination of Information Governance, TRE Builder/Developer and Information Security roles, a threat modelling process and 4 sub-capabilities.

The threat modelling process provides input to the sub-capabilities and informs the controls across the entire architecture by calculating the likelihood and impact of a realised threat.

2.6. Cyber Resilience

What the organisation does to ensure TRE operations continue and recover when threats are realised or an incident occurs.

Figure 16: Cyber Resilience capability decomposition

The resilience process ensures the TRE organisation and infrastructure continues to function when threats are realised, or an incident occurs. Following an incident, the response process is triggered and the organisation reacts to reduce risk. Once the immediate response is complete recovery process is triggered to restore organisation's services to normal operation.

2.7. Vulnerability Management

The ability of the TRE operator to identify, assess, report on, manage and remediate technical vulnerabilities across endpoints, workloads, and systems.

Figure 17: Vulnerability Management capability decomposition

Security patching pre-emptively fixes vulnerabilities within the system usually utilising software vendor issued updates. Patching may also be triggered by the vulnerability scanning or security testing process. One or more vulnerability management applications serve the processes.

2.8. Encryption

The ability of the TRE organisation to deploy and manage encryption to protect information assets, including data for TRE research data.

Figure 18: Encryption capability decomposition

The encryption process is triggered when data is ingressed, egressed or moved within the TRE to ensure it is securely transmitted or stored. The key management application serves the encryption process storing, updating and controlling encryption key data.

2.9. Physical Security

What the organisation does to ensure the physical environment hosting TRE infrastructure is appropriately secured.

Figure 19: Physical Security capability decomposition

Physical access to facilities is controlled through physical security and enforces rules put in place by the identity and access management process.

3.0. Data Management

The ability of the TRE operator to manage data assets and ensure information remains secure.

Figure 20: Data Management capability decomposition

Data management requirements include information governance requirements and researcher requirements. They are defined by the information governance roles and by the owners, users and managers of data.

3.1. Data Lifecycle Management

What the TRE organisation does to manage data assets and ensure information remains secure.

Figure 21: Data Lifecycle Management capability decomposition

The Information Asset Owner is accountable for data assets, with the Data Steward maintaining day-to-day accuracy of the Data Asset Register and Research Metadata. Researchers and Data Consumers interact with Research Data within the boundaries set by classification and minimisation decisions made upstream.

Data Classification is triggered when a new dataset is proposed for ingress, or when a change in regulatory context requires existing assets to be reassessed. Data Ingress is triggered by a request to bring data into the TRE, enforcing controlled and auditable entry of data into the environment. Data Minimisation runs as part of ingress and periodically thereafter, triggered by scheduled review or a change in study scope, ensuring only data necessary for the approved purpose is retained. Data Archiving is triggered by study closure, contract expiry or a scheduled retention review, transitioning data to read-only storage. Data Deletion follows archiving or is triggered directly by an Information Asset Owner instruction or regulatory requirement, with proof of deletion maintained in the register.

The Data Transfer Application supports the ingress and egress processes, providing a controlled channel through which data moves across the TRE boundary updating research metadata and logs automatically.

3.2. Identity and Access Management

The ability of the TRE operator to ensure the right people (identities) can only access the tools and data they need.

Figure 22: Identity and Access Management capability decomposition

Identity and access management processes manage access to data during the data lifecycle. The permission assignment process is triggered by an information asset owner to change permissions for a researcher on research data. This process is served by the access management application. The authentication process identifies users and issues the correct permissions at login.

3.3. Output Management

What the TRE organisation does to manage the checking and release of research outputs from the TRE.

Figure 23: Output Management capability decomposition

The Output Checker role applies disclosure expertise across three interconnected processes. Output Checking is the primary review process, classifying outputs by type and assessing disclosure risk. Where outputs contain statistical or aggregate results, the Statistical Disclosure Control process applies formal techniques, such as suppression and rounding, to reduce re-identification risk. Once approved, the Data Egress process governs the final release, maintaining an auditable record of what left the environment, when, and under whose authority.

Automated Output Checking tooling supports the Output Checker by surfacing common disclosure risks at scale, increasing consistency and throughput without replacing human judgement on complex or novel cases.

3.4. Information Search and Discovery

The ability to query and browse the data within an environment at various levels of abstraction.

Figure 24: Information Search and Discovery capability decomposition

The Data Steward owns and maintains Research Metadata, ensuring it is accurate, complete and conforms to agreed standards. Researchers and Data Consumers use this metadata to locate and evaluate datasets, while the Data Analyst role supports more complex discovery needs, helping interpret data characteristics and assess suitability for specific research questions.

The Metadata Search and Discovery Application brings these roles and data together, providing a query-able interface through which researchers can search across available datasets, create data queries, and, where appropriate, access abstracted or synthetic representations of data without requiring full secure access. This supports earlier and more efficient study design.

4. Supporting Capabilities

Additional capabilities required across the broader organisation to support the TRE

Figure 25: Supporting Capabilities and their associated SATRE requirements

5. Federation Management

The Federation Management pillar is new in SATRE v2.0 and defines what the federation does to govern, coordinate and operate a federation of TREs that work together to support research across multiple organisations.

The federation pillar contains seven capabilities covering the key functions required to operate a safe and effective federation of TREs. These Federation capabilities are specialisations of capabilities in other pillars and so decompositions can be seen in previous sections.

Federation Capability Summary

Federation Capability	Adapts from Pillar(s)	Purpose
5.1 Federation Governance	1.1 Information Governance 1.2 Quality Management 1.3 Risk Management	Adapts information governance, quality and risk management for a multi-party setting; manages member TRE onboarding and the agreements underpinning inter-organisational trust.
5.2 Federation Researcher Accreditation	1.5 Researcher Accreditation 1.6 Training Management and Delivery	Extends researcher and training management to recognise accreditation granted by other federation members, avoiding duplication while maintaining assurance.
5.3 Federation Study Management	1.4 Study Management	Provides a shared project register enabling studies that span multiple TREs to be tracked and governed consistently.
5.4 Federation Information Security	2.5 Information Security 2.7 Vulnerability Management 2.8 Encryption	Extends security, vulnerability management and encryption to operate across federated boundaries; Federation Identities enable consistent authentication and authorisation across member TREs.
5.5 Federation Infrastructure Management	2.2 Infrastructure Management	Coordinates shared infrastructure across federation members to support multi-TRE research operations.
5.6 Federation Data Management	3.2 Identity and Access Management 3.3 Output Management	Manages data assets and ensures information remains secure across the federation, including access control and output management in a multi-party context.
5.7 Federation Financial Management	4.4 Financial Management	Manages the financial arrangements and cost-sharing agreements that sustain the federation.

Capability Descriptions

Federation Governance (5.1) adapts information governance and risk management for a multi-party setting, managing the onboarding of federation members and maintaining the agreements and data that underpin inter-organisational trust.

Federation Researcher Accreditation (5.2) extends researcher and training management to recognise accreditation granted by other federation members, avoiding duplication while maintaining assurance.

Federation Study Management (5.3) provides a shared project register enabling studies that span multiple TREs to be tracked and governed consistently.

Federation Information Security (5.4) extends security, vulnerability management and encryption capabilities to operate across federated boundaries, with Federation Identities as the critical shared data object enabling consistent authentication and authorisation across member TREs.

Federation Infrastructure Management (5.5) coordinates shared and interoperable infrastructure across federation members to support multi-TRE research operations.

Federation Data Management (5.6) manages data assets and ensures information remains secure across the federation, including access control and output management in a multi-party context.

Federation Financial Management (5.7) manages the financial arrangements and cost-sharing agreements that sustain the federation.

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References

1. Baxter, R. (2025) *The TRevolution Profile*. DARE UK. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15479821> (Accessed: 6 June 2026).
2. The Open Group (2023) *ArchiMate® 3.2 Specification*. The Open Group. Available at: <https://publications.opengroup.org/standards/archimate> (Accessed: 6 June 2026).
3. Archi (2024) *Archi – Open Source ArchiMate Modelling*. Available at: <https://www.archimatetool.com/> (Accessed: 6 June 2026).
4. SATRE (2025) *Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE) Specification*. Available at: <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/> (Accessed: 6 June 2026).
5. DARE UK (2025) *Federated Architecture Blueprint*. DARE UK. Available at: <https://dareuk.org.uk/how-we-work/federated-architecture-blueprint/> (Accessed: 6 June 2026).